

ISic3601

I.Sicily inscription 3601

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

tomb in necropolis of Galera-Bagliazzo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR112480

1. οἴμοι ὁ Βύτε

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284878

EDR 112480

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 57.0889

Brugnone, A. 2008. A proposito di un'epigrafe sepolcrale da Selinunte. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 120: 21-28.

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At 91 no.B1

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